

group. The glycoside unlike the aglycone did not give any appreciable shift of the short wavelength band II with fused sodium acetate⁴ showing thereby the absence of free 7-OH group. Evidently the sugar was attached at position 7 of quercetin molecule. The formation of formic acid in the periodate oxidation of the methylated glycoside proved the pyranose ring structure for glucose. The nature of the glycosidic linkage as β was confirmed by hydrolysis with emulsin.

Based on the above data the glycoside could be identified as quercetin-7-O- β -D(+)-glucopyranoside or quercimeritrin. This glycoside has not so far been reported to occur in any other species of this genus.

Compound (D) (Leucodelphinidin) :

The compound was isolated as a buff coloured semi-crystalline solid. It was found to be a polyphenolic and sugar free entity. Pink colour with vanillin-HCl⁵ indicated the presence of free phloroglucinol unit. It gave dark magenta coloured solution on boiling with ethanolic hydrochloric acid which responded to all the colour reactions of naturally occurring 3-hydroxy anthocyanidins. The anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} 557 nm in ethanolic HCl (authentic delphinidin has λ_{\max} 560 nm) and gave bathochromic shift (23 nm) with aluminium chloride^{6,7} (vicinal hydroxyl groups). It was confirmed as delphinidin by cochromatography with an authentic sample. Therefore, the compound (D) λ_{\max} 282 nm and IR similar to the naturally occurring flavan-3 : 4-diols⁸ could be characterised as leucodelphinidin.

Anthocyanin from *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* flowers :

A chocolate coloured compound was isolated from 1% ethanolic hydrochloric acid extract of the yellowish pink flowers of *C. pulcherrima*. It gave positive Molisch test and other reactions characteristic of anthocyanins.

The glycoside on hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid yielded an anthocyanidin which could be precipitated with petroleum ether from amyl alcohol solution into 1% aqueous HCl layer. It crystallised as dark reddish-brown prisms from ethanolic hydrochloric acid mixture and gave colour reactions specific of cyanidin.

The free sugar present in the hydrolysate was identified as D(+)-glucose by its osazone and cochromatography with an authentic sample. Quantitative sugar estimation showed it to be a diglycoside. The anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} at 545 nm (ethanolic HCl), authentic cyanidin has λ_{\max} at 545 nm.) and exhibited bathochromic shift with $AlCl_3$ (presence of vicinal dihydroxyl groups). It was confirmed as cyanidin by co-chromatography with an authentic sample obtained from *Rosagallia* flowers. The anthocyanin had λ_{\max} 532 nm (ethanolic HCl). A hypsochromic shift of 13 nm in the glycoside as

compared to the aglycone was an indication of the probable position of the sugar at 3 & 5 nm. The anthocyanin also compared well with the authentic cyanidin-3 : 5 diglycoside (cyanin) isolated from *Rosa* galla flowers.

Therefore, the presence of cyanin (3:5-diglycoside of cyanidin) in *C. pulcherrima* flowers was confirmed.

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Chemical Investigation of Bark of *Abroma augusta* Linn. (Sterculiaceae).

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ABROMA *augusta* Linn. popularly known as 'Ulat Kambal' grows abundantly in the hotter parts of India. It is also available in the south-eastern region (Baliguni, Nanoor) of the district of Birbhum in West Bengal. The plant is medicinally very important and its roots and root-barks are used as emmenagogue, uterine tonic and in dysmenorrhoea¹. Locally (in the district of Birbhum) its leaves and stem-barks are extensively used in the treatment of gonorrhoea and in the unusually painful and difficult menstruation. The chemical investigation on the roots²⁻⁴ and leaves⁵ of this plant have already been reported but no phytochemical work

seems to have been done on the stem bark of this plant. In view of this fact and its high medicinal utility, a chemical investigation of bark of this plant has been undertaken in this laboratory.

Experimental

Air dried powdered bark of the plant (collected from Baliguni, Nanoor, District Birbhum, W. Bengal) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene. Petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Elution with benzene provided a gummy material which on repeated chromatographies over neutral alumina and silica-gel yielded a white solid m.p. 135°-136°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchardt test and was identified as β -sitosterol by m. m.p. determination; Co-TLC with authentic sample of β -sitosterol and the preparation of its acetate m. p. 127°-28°.

The benzene extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina and on elution with petroleum ether (60-80°) furnished a white crystalline solid m.p. 258°-59° which responds to positive Libermann-Burchardt test for triterpenes. It forms a D.N.P.H. derivative, m.p. 293°-94° (dec). It was identified as friedelin by m.m.p. determination; Co-TLC and Co-IR with authentic specimen of the compound.

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Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Stereospermum suaveolens* DC.

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STEREOSPERMUM *suaveolens* DC. (Bignoniaceae) is distributed throughout India and is reported to have medicinal importance¹. Its different

parts are indigenously used as local remedies for different diseases. The root bark forms an ingredient in dasamula, an Indian preparation used as tonic. Flowers are taken in the form of a confection as an aphrodis. No work seems to have been done on the roots of this plant and hence a systematic study of this part was undertaken. We have obtained lapachol, dehydro- α -lapachone, dehydrotectol and β -sitosterol from the heartwood and β -sitosterol and n-triacontanol from the bark.

Root heartwood: Dried and powdered root heartwood was thoroughly extracted with pet. ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was taken in ether and extracted with 2N-sodium carbonate and separated into acidic and neutral fractions.

Acidic fraction:

Lapachol: The acidic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether=benzene (2:3) afforded lapachol², a yellow compound, m.p. 139-40° (pet. ether); $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$; IR, ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3330 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch), 1660 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch of the quinonoid system). It gave red colouration with alcoholic magnesium acetate and aqueous NaOH.

Neutral fraction:

This was chromatographed over deactivated alumina whereupon the following compounds were obtained.

Dehydrotectol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether yielded dark blue crystals of dehydrotectol³, m.p. 192-3° (MeOH); $C_{29}H_{54}O_4$; I. R., ν_{max}^{KBr} : 1645 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch), identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample. It gave tectol on refluxing with zinc dust.

Dehydro- α -lapachone: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) gave orange needles of dehydro- α -lapachone⁴, m.p. 142-3° (pet. ether); $C_{15}H_{12}O_8$; IR, ν_{max}^{KBr} : 1680 cm^{-1} , 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch of the quinonoid system), 705 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H deformation); identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen.

β -Sitosterol: Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) furnished β -sitosterol; m.p. 136-8° (EtOH); $C_{29}H_{50}O$; acetate (Ac₂O/pyr.) m.p. 126-8°.

Root bark: The finely ground root bark was extracted with petroleum ether and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over deactivated alumina.

β -Sitosterol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 137-8°, identical (mmp, IR and TLC) with an authentic specimen.

A lignan: Further elution with petroleum ether